

Application of FGD process (flue gas desulphurization) to control SO₂ emission at Shree Cement Ltd., Beawar, Rajasthan, India

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Abstract : Laboratory studies were conducted to compare the efficiency by varying the concentration of sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and sludge (waste product of water treatment plant containing CaO) in absorption of SO₂ contained in flue gases which is emitted from thermal power plant of Shree Cement Ltd., Beawar, Rajasthan. All of three situations were cases of absorption coupled with chemical reactions. Thus sodium hydroxide turned out to be better as compared to calcium hydroxide and sludge.

Keywords : Calcium sulphate, flue gas desulphurization, sulphur dioxide, sodium sulphate.

Introduction

The demand of electricity is continuously increasing and it is expected to double in 7-10 years and the pollution in the environment likely to increase in the coming years^{1,2}. The main pollutants from the thermal power plants are dust and objectionable gases like CO, CO₂, SO₂ and NO₂ etc. SO₂ is a major constituent in air pollution to a large extent. Sulphur dioxide produced during combustion of fuels containing sulphur, and affects the environment in number of ways like acid rain, corrosion and severe damages to the health³. A typical 6 MW power generation unit using furnace oil containing 2% sulphur, will emit 388 tons of SO₂ per year based upon 320 working days⁴. A 22.5 MW power generation unit will emit 1690 tons of SO₂ per year. Flue gas desulphurization (FGD) is the current state-of-the-art technology used for removing sulphur dioxide (SO₂) from the exhaust flue gases in power plants⁵. SO₂ is an acid gas and thus the typical sorbent slurries or other materials used to remove the SO₂ from the flue gases are alkaline. The reaction taking place in wet scrubbing using Ca(OH)₂ or NaOH slurry produces CaSO₃ (calcium sulphite) or Na₂SO₃ (sodium sulphite) and can be expressed as⁶ :

Some FGD systems go to a further step and oxidize the CaSO₃ and Na₂SO₃ to produce marketable CaSO₄.2H₂O (gypsum) and Na₂SO₄ (sodium sulphate)⁹.

The present work has been done by capturing SO₂ using sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide, and sludge (waste product of water treatment plant containing CaO). Pet coke with lime stone are being used for power generation in thermal power plant during the experiment in Shree Cement Ltd. SCL is one of the top ten cement producers in India and as a leading player in North Asia. The pet coke having 6% sulphur resulting in emission of SO₂. Therefore experiments has been conducted to trap these gases to produce sulphates. Waste product of WTP, calcium hydroxide, and sodium hydroxide in various permutation and combination has been used with control flow by SO₂ monitoring kit of SO₂ measurement for preparation of calcium sulphate and sodium sulphate. In accordance with the invention, flue gases containing sulphur

dioxide are passed through a solution which was rich with sodium and calcium ions using SO₂ monitoring kit of SO₂ measurement, then SO₂ reacts with these ions to produce respective sulphates. All most complete removal of SO₂ in flue gases has been observed using this process in the Shree Cement Ltd., Beawar, Rajasthan. Prepared CaSO₄ can be used as gypsum, cement production, soil stabilization, and wallboard manufacture. Similarly Na₂SO₄ can also be used as a home laundry detergent, used in paper production. In the laboratory Na₂SO₄ is used as an inert drying agent, for removing traces of water from organic solutions⁷⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. All experiments were conducted on stack monitoring kit (Model No. and Make-VSS1, 141 DTH-2005, Vayubodhan). First of all stack monitoring kit of SO₂ monitoring was set up for experiment at chimney inlet of Boiler No. 4 of SCL. Flue gas containing SO₂ was supplied from chimney via probe connected with flexible pipe of stack monitoring kit. The flow of flue gas was controlled using an inlet line rota meter and was maintained at a value of 3 liter per minute¹⁰ and other end of flexible pipe carrying air and SO₂ respectively was connected to a impinger of 10 cm diameter and 100 cm length. The impinger was filled with 100 ml of scrubbing media in this experiment i.e. sludge solution, calcium hydroxide solution, sodium hydroxide solution. The concentration of SO₂ in flue gases was first measured by stack monitoring kit. Five sets of reading were taken by varying concentration of every solution. 100 ml of solution was taken in first two different impinges for better absorption of SO₂ and 30 ml of H₂O₂ was taken in the third for determination of remaining SO₂. Respective sulphate has been formed in solution. Dissolved sulphate can be extracted from solution by heating till dryness. Three parameters regards to % SO₃ (gravimetric), % SO₂ (volumetric) and % alkali-ny have been analyzed in precipitate. The methods used as Indian standard method from Bureau of Indian Standard¹¹⁻¹⁵.

Operating condition of SO₂ absorption is given in Table 1. Experimental set up shown in Fig. 6.

Table 1. Operating condition of SO₂ absorption in scrubbing media

Sl. no.	Operating condition	Value
1.	Initial concentration of scrubbing media	Varying
2.	pH of solution	Varying
3.	Total liquid hold up	100 ml
4.	Temperature of solution	25 °C
5.	Time period for reaction	Varying
6.	Flow of flue gas in impinger	3 LPM
7.	SO ₂ load in flue gas	3000-3200 ppm
8.	Flue gas temperature	135 °C
9.	Flue gas flow in duct of ESP O/L	150522 M ³ /h
10.	Pet coke feeding rate	13 Ton/h
11.	Lime stone feeding rate	1.0 Ton/h

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 and Table 2 reports that relation between recovery of absorption of SO₂ using varying concentration of sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and sludge. As can be seen from Fig. 1 that recovery of SO₂ using calcium hydroxide and sludge is far below that using sodium hydroxide. Fig. 2 and Table 3 shows the results of % SO₃ (gravimetric) of precipitate which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂ contained in flue gases. It is reported that % SO₂ is higher in case of NaOH as to others. Fig. 3 and Table 4 shows the results of % SO₂ (volumetric) of precipitate which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂ contained in flue gases. It is reported that % SO₂ is higher in case of NaOH as to

Fig. 1. Comparative study of recovery of SO₂ with three different reagents : (●) recovery of SO₂ using sludge (%), (■) recovery of SO₂ using Ca(OH)₂ (%), (▲) recovery of SO₂ using NaOH (%).

Table 2. Relation between concentration of different reagents and recovery of SO₂

Sl. no.	Concentration of reagent (%)	Recovery of SO ₂ using sludge (%)	Recovery of SO ₂ using calcium hydroxide (%)	Recovery of SO ₂ using sodium hydroxide (%)
1.	5	62.56	-	97.96
2.	10	60.18	80.15	95.08
3.	15	52.08	76.20	90.18
4.	20	42.25	70.85	88.02
5.	25	40.16	64.18	85.19
6.	30	30.28	58.06	-

Table 3. Analysis results of precipitate (% SO₂ gravimetric) which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂

Sl. no.	Concentration of reagent (%)	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by sludge	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by Ca(OH) ₂	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by NaOH
1.	5	-	-	20.76
2.	10	3.26	5.15	5.67
3.	15	3.06	4.42	1.49
4.	20	2.15	4.32	0.52
5.	25	1.82	2.96	0.24
6.	30	1.02	2.46	-

Table 4. Analysis results of precipitate (% SO₂ volumetric) which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂

Sl. no.	Concentration of reagent (%)	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by sludge	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by Ca(OH) ₂	Analysis results of precipitate (% SO ₂) which was prepared by NaOH
1.	5	-	-	39.21
2.	10	2.60	4.12	25.61
3.	15	2.44	3.53	20.54
4.	20	1.72	3.45	19.47
5.	25	1.45	2.36	17.62
6.	30	0.81	1.96	-

Table 5. Analysis results of precipitate (% CaSO₄ and % Na₂SO₄) which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂

Sl. no.	Concentration of reagent (%)	% CaSO ₄ which was prepared by sludge	% CaSO ₄ which was prepared by Ca(OH) ₂	% Na ₂ SO ₄ which was prepared by NaOH
1.	5	-	-	35.49
2.	10	5.54	8.75	17.01
3.	15	5.20	7.51	9.81
4.	20	3.65	7.34	5.77
5.	25	3.09	5.03	3.99
6.	30	1.73	4.18	-

others. Fig. 4 and Table 5 show the results of % respective sulphate of precipitate which was prepared by three different reagents and % SO₂ in flue gases. Fig. 5 and Table 6 shows

the results of % alkalinity of precipitate which was prepared by three different reagents. We know that alkalinity is the reverse of % SO₂ and it is confirmed by Fig. 5.

Table 6. Analysis results of precipitate (% alkalinity) which was prepared by three different reagents and SO₂

Sl. no.	Concentration of reagent (%)	% Alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by sludge	% Alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by Ca(OH) ₂	% Alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by NaOH
1.	5	-	-	0.62
2.	10	0.0014	0.0200	1.17
3.	15	0.0028	0.0216	1.64
4.	20	0.0144	0.0252	1.58
5.	25	0.0158	0.0324	1.75
6.	30	0.0201	0.0540	-

Fig. 2. Comparative study of concentration of three different reagents with % SO₃ (gravimetric) of precipitate : (•) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₃) which was prepared by sludge, (■) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₃) which was prepared by Ca(OH)₂, (▲) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₃) which was prepared by NaOH.

Fig. 3. Comparative study of concentration of three different reagents with % SO₂ (volumetric) of precipitate : (•) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₂) which was prepared by sludge, (■) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₂) which was prepared by Ca(OH)₂, (▲) analysis results of precipitate (% SO₂) which was prepared by NaOH.

Fig. 4. Comparative study of concentration of three different reagents with % SO₄ of precipitate : (•) % CaSO₄ which was prepared by sludge, (■) % CaSO₄ which was prepared by Ca(OH)₂, (▲) % Na₂SO₄ which was prepared by NaOH.

Fig. 5. Comparative study of concentration of three different reagents with % alkalinity : (•) % alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by sludge, (■) % alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by Ca(OH)₂, (▲) % alkalinity in precipitate which was prepared by NaOH.

Conclusion :

(A) The recovery of SO₂ using sludge (waste product) found is very low. The probable reasons may be :

Fig. 6. Experimental set up by using SO₂ monitoring kit for absorption of SO₂

(i) The pH of the all solution was between 4.5–4.8. Hence SO₂ absorption is restricted due to the nature of SO₂ is acidic and reaction should be carried out in alkaline solution.

(ii) As the sludge sample is insoluble in water so the % CaO is very low in all solutions around 0.3 percent. To avoid pH problem, calcium hydroxide were taken for further experiments due to high pH.

(B) The recovery of SO₂ using calcium hydroxide found little higher as compare to sludge. The probable reasons may be :

(i) The pH of the all solution was between 9.1–9.5. Hence SO₂ absorption has been taken place in Ca(OH)₂ solution.

(ii) The colour change of solution was easily seen during the experiment i.e. initial colour was white, but after passing of SO₂ colour was yellow.

(iii) The maximum recovery of SO₂ was obtained with 10% Ca(OH)₂ solution. Therefore it seems to be optimum. The recovery of SO₂ in higher concentration of

Ca(OH)₂ solution was not obtained due to insolubility of Ca(OH)₂ in DM water. To avoid solubility problem, NaOH were taken for further experiments due to completely solubility.

(C) The maximum recovery of SO₂ was obtain in 5% NaOH solution while less in higher concentration of NaOH. The probable reasons are :

(i) The nature of SO₂ is acidic, so it reduces the pH of solution in half an hour. Hence further SO₂ absorption is not possible. Therefore it is concluded that if 5% NaOH solution is sprayed in the path of flue gases then we can recover maximum SO₂ and protect the environment from pathogenic effect of SO₂ and yield sulphate also.

(ii) The lower concentration of the reagent is found to be optimum. Increasing concentration of solution is not very fruitful for maximum absorption of SO₂ in exhaust flue gases. This is because of load of SO₂ in flue gases is very low (at ppm level). Hence the reagents remains as it is in solution after completely absorption of SO₂.

(iii) From the comparative study of three different

reagents regarding to removal of SO_2 , it is observed that sodium hydroxide is superior as compare to calcium hydroxide and sludge. The initial rate of absorption is higher for sodium hydroxide as compared to calcium hydroxide and sludge. All the absorption methods coupled with a chemical reaction.

(iv) It may be suggested that sulphur dioxide is a weak acid and it is a well known fact that reaction of a weak acid with a strong base is fast, meaning stronger the base faster would be the reaction.

(v) Therefore sodium hydroxide is a strong base compared to calcium hydroxide and sludge so this evident that sodium hydroxide is a better solvent for removal of SO_2 .

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